

IMPLEMENTATION MODEL OF POLICY ON ACCESS TO ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT INFORMATION AT THE BANTEN PROVINCE ENVIRONMENT AND FORESTRY SERVICE

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to describe, disclose, and analyze the implementation of the PROPER public information access openness policy in environmental management at the Banten Province Environment and Forestry Service and produce a model for implementing PROPER information access openness policies in effective environmental management at the Provincial Environment and Forestry Service. Banten. This study uses a qualitative method with a case study design. The study results reveal that the policy on access to information disclosure in the Proper assessment in Banten Province has not achieved its objectives because the company tends to be an object rather than a subject. The community, as the target group of the implementing organization, only receives the results of the company's environmental performance assessment without being directly involved, so activities carried out by local government officials together with the centre do not provide opportunities for the public to participate and ensure sustainable environmental development and create a green economy. Furthermore, the researchers found a model, namely the synthesis/hybrid model, which is a mixed model in which the implementation of access to information disclosure Properly elaborates on interventions from the central government with community participation; even though the policy is decentralized, the central government still has a role in controlling and overseeing the implementation of corporate environmental governance assessments based on in conditions that require resource utilization strategies. The existence of moral responsibility to provide welfare for future generations in Banten Province.

Keywords: Policy Implementation, Access to Information Disclosure, Implementation of Company Performance Rating (PROPER), Environmental Management.

A. INTRODUCTION

The concept of environmentally sustainable development implies that everyone bears obligations and responsibilities to future generations and each other in one generation (Elkington, 1994; Langhelle, 1999) and requires the preservation of environmental functions and capabilities as a foundation for sustainable development (Elkington, 1994; Langhelle, 1999). Dobson, 2007; Stagl, 2007). However, the reality shows that environmental degradation or degradation continues to occur, including environmental pollution due to liquid waste from industrial activities, hospitals, domestic waste that has not been appropriately managed and air pollution originating from mobile sources (motor vehicles), non-permanent sources—moving from factory chimneys and forest fires (Howard, 1991; Bovenberg & Smulders, 1995).

On the other hand, population growth that is constantly increasing can result in a decrease in environmental quality. Environmental degradation will always be the most urgent Problem to be solved (Suhrke, 1994; Zhang & Wen, 2008). On the other hand, the intensity of economic activities such as industry and manufacturing has resulted in a heavy level of environmental damage and pollution. To ensure that environmental management is running well, all interested

parties must be involved (Afroza et al., 2003; Reed, 2008). Good governance is the main prerequisite for sound environmental management and optimal sustainable development (Lockwood, 2010; Islam et al, 2017). The synergy of the strengths of good governance which includes elements of the government, the private sector and the community makes public administration able to display reliable performance in serving the community. According to Brinkerhoff & Brinkerhoff (2011), the government will be able to carry out its functions within the framework of good governance, if a cooperative public administration system is created with a public service approach that is more relevant to the community.

National Conference on Sustainable Development in January 2004 in Yogyakarta. One of the agreements reached and accepted at the conference was to develop and utilize communication and information (Hardjasoemantri, 2005). In the context of environmental management, developing and utilizing communication and information is not only understood as an effort to provide information linearly in one direction, from top to bottom (top-down) or vice versa (bottom-up) but how the exchange of information flows occurs interactively (dialogically) (Kurniawan, 2006).

Open access to information is one of the efforts made by the government to control the negative impacts of development on the environment. Open access is the community's right to participate in the development and improve their quality of life (Tews et al, 2003; Irvin & Stansbury, 2004). The right to environmental information will increase the value of the effectiveness of participation in environmental management and open opportunities for the community to actualize their right to a good and healthy environment (Reed, 2008; Zhang et al, 2008). As an ideal policy, the interaction between the government and the community in every development activity in the form of information about a policy is necessary (Seyfang & Smith, 2007; Woolcock & Narayan, 2000).

Open access to information is one of the mechanisms to control the performance of environmental tools. One of the environmental tools launched and continuously implemented by the government. The Company Performance Rating Program in Environmental Management (PROPER) is a form of policy instrument developed by the State Ministry of Environment (KLH) to encourage compliance and concern for companies in environmental management. (Nurputri & Nuzula, 2019). PROPER is one of the complementary instruments for evaluating the performance of corporate environmental management, based on the thought and analysis that efforts to improve corporate compliance performance will be more effective through applying policy mixed instruments (Bundojo & Davianti, 2019).

In addition, the application of PROPER can answer the need for access to information, transparency, and public participation in environmental management (Fahmawati & Purnaweni, 2018). PROPER aims to encourage companies to comply with environmental regulations and achieve environmental excellence (environmental excellence) through the integration of sustainable development principles in production and service processes by implementing environmental management systems, 3Rs, energy efficiency, resource conservation and ethical business implementation and responsible for the community through community development programs (Manala, 2017).

PROPER, in its assessment process, emphasizes the output control approach. (MOE, 2005; Rothery, 2006). PROPER uses compliance and information instruments as benchmarks for evaluating the performance of a company's environmental management performance. The instrument of compliance is regulated through the Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2021 concerning the Company Performance Rating Program in Environmental Management. The performance rating system used by PROPER is grouped into 5 colour levels, namely 1. Gold, 2. Green, 3. Blue, 4. Red and 5. Black. Companies rated gold, green and blue are included in the ranking of environmentally compliant companies. Red and black companies have not obeyed (Utomo, 2019).

The results of the initial observations of researchers suspected that the transparency of access to the PROPER information in Banten Province was less transparent. So that the community, as the target group, views the policy as not meeting expectations because they are not involved in controlling or managing the environment in Prov. Banten. This situation encourages people to access the existing gaps, but this is not easy. It is difficult for the public to directly access information regarding the progress of the assessment (P2LPB, 2019). The results of the PROPER assessment should be informed through media, both print and electronic media, as well as cyber media such as websites and social media. In addition to environmental complaints, PROPER also receives information services.

Legal guarantees for providing and obtaining information in Indonesia are still very weak, and the procedures for accessing it are still unclear, so it is not easy for the public to access information (Retnowati, 2012; Kristiyanto, 2016). Witoelar (2005) stated that PROPER was launched by the Ministry of Environment (KLH) as a form of supervision and effort for transparency and community involvement in environmental management. Dissemination of company performance results in the community and community involvement as social control in managing environmental impacts (Rosyida & Nasdian, 2011). The community can participate in environmental management, which is one of the determining pillars of sustainable development (Salim, 2009). Information instruments allow the community to participate accurately and actively in controlling environmental impacts (Kahfi, 2015).

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the implementation model of PROPER information access openness in realizing environmental development in Banten Province, where empirically, the policy has not been implemented effectively. While the sub-focus is that the ineffectiveness of the implementation of the PROPER information access policy in realizing environmental development in Banten Province mentioned above will be studied and explored based on the Smith & Larimer (2018) policy implementation model consisting of idealized policy, target group, implementing organization, and environmental factors.

B. METHOD

The research method used by the researcher is a qualitative research method with a case study approach, namely research events, basic things (real-life events), which are ongoing, not something that has passed, meaning that the data collected is not a collection of numbers, but rather from in-depth interviews, observation activities, field notes, official documents and others (Herdiansyah, 2015). Case study research makes it possible to investigate a particular event, situation, or social condition and to provide insight into the process that explains how a particular event or situation occurred (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). They explain that case studies of individuals, groups, and communities help show the important things of concern, the social processes of the community in concrete events, and the stakeholders' experiences. Cases can illustrate how problems can be addressed through research.

Based on the thoughts above, the researcher tries to explore what information can be learned or drawn from the case of the implementation of PROPER information access openness in Prov. Banten, by making direct observations and being directly involved. One of the essential things to consider in choosing a case, the researcher believes that from the case of implementing PROPER information access openness, further and in-depth scientific knowledge can be obtained.

The process of processing and analyzing qualitative data is carried out in stages, including data reduction, where the data obtained is written in the form of a detailed description, then reduced, summarized, selected the main ones, focused on the essential things, found themes or patterns, and arranged more systematically. Then the data presentation or display is arranged systematically based on the type and pattern, then arranged in charts or narratives to form a series of meaningful information according to the Problem. As for drawing conclusions and verification, it means that after the reduction and presentation of the data is carried out, conclusions are drawn or verification is carried out.

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of the Policy on Opening Access to Environmental Management Information at PROPER in Banten Province

Implementing the policy on access to information disclosure of the Corporate Performance Rating Assessment Program (PROPER) in Environmental Management in Banten Province still shows the phenomenon and dynamics of the gap between the policy platform and policy implementation. Environment through the Department of Environment and Forestry (DLHK) then delegate authority to the governor of the provincial government. The process of assessing and determining companies that perform well or otherwise in the PROPER framework is still dominated by provincial decisions. PROPER is one of the policy tools developed by the Ministry of Environment (KLH) to encourage the compliance of the person in charge of businesses and/or activities to various laws and regulations in the environmental sector through information instruments by actively involving the community. Therefore, PROPER is closely related to the dissemination of information on the compliance performance of each company

to all stakeholders on a national scale. In other words, PROPER is a Public Disclosure Program for Environmental Compliance. Therefore, the PROPER policy is closely related to the provision of environmental information by the person in charge of the business to the community so that the public can actively respond to information on a company's PROPER compliance level by providing a detailed response (good or bad), based on the PROPER information. This community response is expected to encourage companies further to improve their environmental protection and management performance.

Ideal Policy Factors

This idealized policy stage is the first stage in policy implementation that shows the extent to which the government's interaction pattern with the community is the first indicator initiated by policymakers to encourage, influence and encourage the target group to implement it (Smith & Larimer, 2018). At this stage, we want to know the extent of the interaction carried out by the Banten Provincial government with the community and then the extent of information about policies as the second indicator, in this case, the Banten Provincial Regulation No. 10 of 2012, concerning Environmental Protection and Management. Inter-implementation communication is the third indicator related to access to public information disclosure to the PROPER team of the Environment and Forestry Service (DLHK) which is an extension of the KLH, for the community in the area to be accepted by the community and how the interaction between policy implementers is.

The existence of a PROPER policy is considered ideal from the conditions above; with the implementation of the PROPER program, the company must meet the criteria that must be complied with. The critical thing that reassures the public about efforts to overcome environmental damage through the PROPER compliance program is access to information disclosure for the public, which can be gradually achieved. PROPER evaluates companies throughout Indonesia according to the criteria they have. Therefore, people from all regions in Indonesia can monitor the performance of surrounding companies in environmental management. Both those that have been assessed and those that have not been assessed. To maintain the accountability of the PROPER assessment, the assessment process is carried out in a graded assessment system. Starting from a review by the PROPER KLH Technical Team. This is followed by a review of the technical team with the Provincial and Regency or City Governments to provide the latest information on the company's environmental management performance.

The ideal PROPER policy is expected not to deviate from the desired target because it has clear and consistent standards with the expectations of the Banten Provincial Government. This means that the ideal PROPER policy carried out by the Office, Ministry of LHK through DLHK, and the community does not deviate from the goals and objectives outlined in the planning because it is always stated in every proposal submitted so that its implementation does not confuse, especially in the interpretation of the expected policy. The ideal policy seen from the successful implementation of the PROPER assessment program is more determined by the consistency of the program, especially for determining the priority scale, determining target

groups, target group support, standard operating procedures, flexibility, information support, and networking between the Department, DLHK, and the people of Banten Province.

The implementation of the PROPER policy, consistent with the vision and mission of the Governor of Banten, is gradually in line with what is expected; information on the company's agenda in managing environmental impacts that are needed by the community can be obtained adequately. However, when referring to the results of the development of the environmental sector, it seems that the ideal internal policies of the Department, Ministry of Environment and Forestry, and NGOs/Communities of Banten Province are still limited to writing or slogans, which have not been fully implemented in the policy on access to information disclosure PROPER Banten Province. At the same time, the core vision and mission are made solely to be implemented in policies so that the development of the environmental sector creates comfort for the people of Banten Province.

Considering that this program is considered to have succeeded in increasing community participation and making environmental development improvements throughout the Banten Province, the routine and continuity of this program are supported by the DPRD, namely that every year it is accommodated in the General Budget Policy document and Temporary Budget Ceiling Priorities and on the Banten Provincial Budget.

Target Group Factors

In the context of policy indicators according to expectations, it means that public expectations or also known as public expectations are an essential element of sound and democratic environmental sector decision-making. People's expectations for organized and systematic environmental management must be channeled or aspirated to the government as a target group. This encourages the government to actively fulfil public aspirations by implementing adaptive environmental policies. Currently, recognition of the process of participation and guaranteeing community rights can be seen at every level of policy, both internationally, regionally, nationally, and locally (Malek & Costa, 2015).

The PROPER program, as part of a sustainable environment-based green industry development program, provides open access to information so that participation in development increases and can protect the community from the impact of pollution and other damage based on a community protection assessment approach through increasing the role of industrial companies, under development. Then the PROPER target group is a group of people or organizations in the community who will receive goods or services whose behaviour will be influenced by policies; in this case, community or public satisfaction is the goal of development, with a clear commitment between the government and the community and each can play a role following their duties and responsibilities. The implementation of policies can run optimally.

The first and most important indicator of the target group stage is whether the policy aligns with expectations. In every maintenance and repair of environmental infrastructure implemented by the Ministry, Service, and NGOs for the benefit of the community as the target group, the achievements can be seen from the aspects of understanding, managerial expertise,

skills, ability to absorb technology, expectations, attitudes, and desire to partner, committed awareness, and policy socialization. Moreover, guarantees, Ministries, Dinas, and target group implementers must be sensitive about their expectations. At the target group stage, it is essential to ascertain whether the policy is in line with expectations and the extent of policy implementers' roles and priorities. In this case, resources in policy implementation play an essential role because policy implementation will not be effective if supporting sources are unavailable.

In the context of the operational realm, the second policy priority is how PROPER governance is carried out and the extent to which the government consistently ensures all provisions so that the program target group feels the program's benefits as expected. PROPER is a Public Disclosure Program for Environmental Compliance. PROPER is not a substitute for existing conventional compliance instruments, such as civil and criminal environmental law enforcement. This program is complementary and in synergy with other compliance instruments. Thus, efforts to improve environmental quality can be carried out more efficiently and effectively.

PROPER is a form of government policy to improve the company's environmental management performance following what has been stipulated in the legislation. Furthermore, PROPER is also a manifestation of transparency and democratization in environmental management in Indonesia. The application of this instrument is an effort by the State Ministry of the Environment to implement some of the principles of good governance (transparency, fairness, accountability, and community involvement) in environmental management.

Implementing Organizational Factors

The first indicator of the implementing organization dimension is a responsibility as a manager, which means that from a constitutional perspective, state power is related to responsibilities and obligations in any field, including environmental management. Juridically on all things that become the object of his control. Because even if such state power is associated with the aspect of the clause that power does not mean possessing, the aspect of control is identical to possessing. If described in another language, such state power in a more realistic aspect will appear to be mastering, or by mastering is possessing. The boundary between the two is so thin that it is almost indistinguishable. Therefore, according to the adage of law, whoever controls it owns it; he is always responsible. The implementing organization for the PROPER program simultaneously acts as the person in charge of it, consisting of the Office, BPLHD, NGOs, and the community involved in each district/city area of Banten Province. The person in charge of implementing the policy of open access to environmental PROPER information is more oriented towards encouraging industry-based companies to implement green management of corporate waste and to determine sustainable environmental quality standards. Open access to information for the public is a stage to see the extent of the responsibility for managing and supervising industry-based companies. Implementers responsible for implementation can be in the form of organizations or individuals who carry out policies in the field by serving as managers, implementation, and supervisors. Starting in 1996, the PROPER award was given based on an assessment tool based on Law no. 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection

and Management and Regulation of the State Minister of the Environment No. 05 of 2011 concerning PROPER. The responsibility for managing the assessment is then handed over to the provincial government through the SKPD, in this case, the Environment and Forestry Service. The facts show that implementing the company's performance rating assessment program is also the responsibility of all components of society. In this study, information was obtained that the Department of Environment and Forestry always coordinates with the sub-district government. Village/kelurahan government, then the village government consults with community members so that the implementation of the company performance rating program located in the village involves representatives of the community as observers, although the governance corporate governance that has an impact on the environment using modern processing systems and company experts as implementers in the field.

Supervision of environmental management is seen from the institutions that are controlled and those that carry out control can be divided into "internal control" (internal control) and "external control" (external control). Internal control (internal control) is supervision carried out by an agency/organ that is structurally still an organization within the government. This form of control can be classified as technical-administrative control or built-in control. While external control (external control) in environmental management is supervision carried out by the agency/organ in an organizational structure outside the government in the executive sense. For example; Controls that are carried out directly, such as social control carried out by the community through Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) that are concerned with the environment, as well as reactive controls that are carried out indirectly through the judiciary, in this case, the general courts and administrative courts.

Thus, the policy implementing organization with indicators of responsibility as a manager, responsibility as an implementer, and responsibility as supervisor, in terms of being in charge, there are still weak elements in implementing the PROPER policy, so improvement efforts are needed to be in line with the expectations of the people of the Province Banten.

Environmental Factors

The environmental component, in this sense, prioritizes the environment, which plays a significant role in the effectiveness of policy implementation. The existence of the environment, in this case, is a strategic factor internally and externally that can function as a supporter of the success of the policy implementation process so that the goals of public policy are achieved, as well as have the potential to be an obstacle to the policy implementation process that causes policy implementation to fail. The existence of an assessment of environmental aspects in the operation of industrial-based companies protected by law is expected to improve the quality of the regional environment. Program environment that influences policy implementation such as cultural, social, economic and political as well as ecological aspects. The extent to which the external environment contributes to the success of the public policy. Much attention has been focused on the impact of the social, economic, and political environment on public policy by identifying the influence of environmental variables that can affect policy outcomes or outputs. At this stage, the company's environmental management has not yet been able to see changes in the cultural, social, economic, and political

patterns of the community because the PROPER program has only analyzed the impact of PROPER on the company as the person in charge of the business, not yet on the relationship between the results of the PROPER assessment to the potentially affected community. In addition, the community has not been involved in monitoring the company's performance. The community still provides information voluntarily, so environmental management through social control has not been implemented significantly.

In terms of environmental factors, it can be observed how far the effect of implementing access to information disclosure on company performance assessment in the PROPER framework on social, cultural, political and economic aspects can be observed that society is a social being that tends to change and undergo a process towards psychological and spiritual maturity. Physique. The community is led to constantly change from a society with a simple social order to a modern, independent, and innovative social order to encourage the region's progress and course. Such conditions are not easy because people with rural characteristics tend to be static and do not follow changes quickly, including access to information technology that is now growing.

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion as described above, the researcher can criticize the theory put forward by Smith (1973) that the idealized policy is favourable, the target group has not acted as a subject, the implementing organization has not met public expectations, and environmental factors in the implementation of access policies. Information disclosure on PROPER environmental governance assessments for companies in Banten Province has not been running effectively. The Banten Provincial Government, through the Banten Provincial Environment and Forestry Service and other related institutions, can pay more attention to social, economic, and political conditions in carrying out environmental development because environmental development is not only for the development of economic aspects but also supports social development, culture and ecological systems.

2. Barriers to the Implementation of the Policy on Access to Environmental Management Information Openness at PROPER in Banten Province

The results of the study noted several factors that caused the implementation of access to information disclosure PROPER not to be practical, namely the policy of information disclosure with legal instruments in stages from the law on the environment, the Minister of Environment Regulation concerning Corporate Assessment of Environmental Compliance through PROPER, not yet supported by Regulations. Banten Province Regarding PROPER Assessment, the implementation in the region is still not optimal. The authority of the Regional Government, namely the Banten Province Environment and Forestry Service, in the implementation of PROPER is limited to the submission of proposed Blue & Green candidate ratings for gold rank, namely the highest rank in PROPER is still managed by the Central Government, namely the Ministry of Environment. The capacity of the PROPER team in field surveys and company assessment activities to formulate rankings and publications for winning companies with specific categories cannot be said to have increased. The technical team has not been supported by staff with environmental education background with environmental auditor competence. Not all evaluator teams can carry out evaluation activities, such as Head

of Division and Head of Section officials, due to time constraints or other technical obstacles, so other teams work with uneven workloads. Regarding budget resources, the budget for field visits and sampling has been eliminated with the refocus on handling Covid-19 in the last three years. Sampling for the PROPER assessment is only through a sample (Web-based) and does not reflect the facts on the ground. There is no budget allocation for the discussion of blue and green proposals in supervision which is only through zoom, which is not optimal. Community involvement in the PROPER assessment is an intermediate goal to realize linear corporate environmental governance and safeguard the interests of the community from environmental destruction practices and unsustainable environmental governance. In terms of the PROPER assessment, the public still encounters difficulties accessing information, so they cannot verify the program, actualize the progress of activities and criticize in the form of a transparent and accountable evaluation of the PROPER assessment. So far, PROPER has only provided information in one direction, namely through the website. This has helped quite a lot, but only for those with broad internet access. It is different with the people who mostly live around the company's location. Most of these people, most of them do not have easy internet access. In addition to internet access, some people are not used to computer-based technology. Therefore, the transparency of the assessment is still considered inadequate.

Community support as one of the conditions for successful policy implementation, in the context of the PROPER assessment, has not been achieved optimally; this arises as a result of the lack of community involvement in its activities; the program is more elitist and has prominence as a scientific program. So far, there has been no particular socialization from the central and local governments related to PROPER. Whether the centre carries it out to the regions, the regions to the community, as well as from the centre of the regions to NGOs, mentoring and other community leaders. The informants said that working with community representatives would facilitate PROPER's work. Where are the limitations of the PROPER team in carrying out activities, especially in the field?

3. PROPER Information Access Openness Policy Implementation Model on Environmental Management in Banten Province

Researchers found a novelty synthesis/hybrid model, which is a mixed model in which the implementation of access to information disclosure PROPER in Banten Province elaborates intervention from the central government with community participation; even though the policy is decentralized but the central government still has a role in controlling and overseeing the assessment of corporate environmental governance through the PROPER mechanism in Banten Province. Access to information disclosure for the public to view and participate in the company's assessment in managing environmental aspects is not only for economic development but also for supporting integrated socio-cultural and ecological systems. This integrated and sustainable environmental development is also generally based on conditions that require resource utilization strategies and moral responsibility to provide welfare for future generations. In other words, development like this is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the right to meet the needs of future generations in Banten

Province. For more details, the findings of the Synthesis/Hybrid model in the implementation of the PROPER information disclosure access policy in Banten Province are as follows:

Figure 1: Synthesis/Hybrid Model Implementation of the Openness Policy on Access to Environmental Management information at PROPER in Banten Province

Based on Figure 1, it can be explained that the Synthesis/Hybrid model in policy implementation, according to the researchers, is the most appropriate because this approach is not only from the central government but also the participation of the community; this can overcome the "Implementation Gap", where the policies that the government has made can respond well by the community. The most important thing is that the implementation of this policy must show the effectiveness of the policy itself. The realization of access to information on environmental management by companies on a broad and sustainable basis in Banten Province is meant that the management of the company's environmental impacts is carried out without compromising the needs of a healthy environment from the community and instead builds economic and social justice in an integrated and sustainable or sustainable manner. Also generally based on conditions that require resource utilization strategies and the existence of a moral responsibility to provide welfare for future generations. Successful implementation (Successful Implementation) is the development of a sustainable environment and a green economy (go green). This development meets the needs of the present without compromising the right to meet the needs of future generations in Banten Province. This is because implementing the PROPER access to information disclosure policy in Banten Province aims to leave economic practices that emphasize short-term profits and hurt the environment, become environmentally friendly economic practices and meet the needs of the present

generation without compromising the ability of future generations. Green Economy Development is not only about converting energy and reducing carbon emissions but also about efficient use of resources, expanding market demand and creating new economic growth fields to create social balance. Implementing environmental policies oriented to Problem Solving through public transparency and environmental development targets in Banten Province to improve the quality and quantity of the environment will be easily achieved with community involvement or participation. As the policy implementer, the government should place the community as the policy subject. In the context of the target group, participation is interpreted as community participation in supporting and succeeding in policies and programs initiated by the government. Transparency participation is the community's right to be involved at every stage of development, starting from planning, implementation, and supervision in environmental conservation so that the community is not just a beneficiary or a mere object but an agent of development (subjects).

D. CONCLUSION

Implementing the policy on access to information disclosure in the Company Performance Rating Assessment Program (PROPER) in Banten Province has not been optimal in achieving its goals because information and communication related to the PROPER program have not gone well, not many people at large are aware of PROPER. The community, as the target group of the implementing organization, only accepts the results of the company's environmental performance assessment without being directly involved in the PROPER assessment, so the principles of participation, openness, fairness and responsibility cannot be applied. Organizations implementing the PROPER program do not pay attention to the expectations and greater involvement of the community, so all activities carried out by local government officials and the center do not provide opportunities for the public to participate and ensure sustainable environmental development and realize a green economy. The synthesis/hybrid model is a mixed model in which the implementation of the PROPER policy by elaborating the intervention of the central government with community participation; even though the policy is decentralized, the central government still has a role in controlling and supervising the implementation of corporate environmental governance in Banten Province. Whereas the hybrid model that brings together the political will of the central government, which is the top-down policy with social interest that is bottom-up, needs to be strengthened by participatory policies in Banten Province to support the ecological system through the operation of environmentally friendly, sustainable companies, and create a green economy.

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